

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

Transforming the response to Hematological Diseases by seizing the power of Artificial Intelligence

An open hub for clinicians and researchers to work together defining, developing and validating AI models to improve the way we currently diagnose and treat hematological diseases

INNOVATION

INTEROPERABILITY

TRUST

SCALABILITY

3 clinical use cases in Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS),
Multiple Myeloma (MM) and Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

DIAGNOSIS

PROGNOSIS

TREATMENT

23

partners

8

countries

4

years

€10M

in funding

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